

DELIVERABLE 1.4

COLLATED REFLEXIVE MONITORING AND DYNAMIC EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

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0. GLOSSARY

CLIC: The CLIC framework is the primary conceptual basis where the project is rooted as a central reference to the guidelines. The CLIC framework will guide policy-, planning- and practice-based interventions in urban food environments (and associated urban food systems) that deliver sustainability **Co-benefits**, strengthen rural-urban **Linkages**, enhance social **Inclusion** and create new **Connectivities** between food and other complex systems (see figure 1). The CLIC is explicitly a normative framework; it outlines a direction of travel for food sustainability agendas by emphasizing four key dimensions of social, environmental, spatial and sectoral ‘integration’. It also allows for comparative studies within the FoodCLIC project as well as monitoring and evaluating food system transformation along the project time horizon and beyond.

City-region food system (CRFS): “In general, the city region is understood as a given geographical region that includes one or more urban centres and their surrounding peri-urban and rural hinterland across which flows of people, food, goods, resources and ecosystem services are happening. A CRFS encompasses all food system actors and activities taking place in the city region and over which the local/regional government have planning and intervention powers”. This concept rests upon the idea that increasing support for food localization around an urban center and its rural hinterlands is critical to transitioning towards sustainability.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO): The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) is a specialized agency of the United Nations that leads international efforts to defeat hunger. <https://www.fao.org/>

Food deprived and vulnerable groups: People whose diets are lacking in quantity or nutritional quality (resulting in food safety risks and undernutrition) on account of limited access as a result of spatiality (e.g., living in ‘food deserts’), living on low income and/or personal circumstances (e.g., institutionalized persons, single-parent families).

Food Policy Network (FPN): A (to be) formalized network of committed organizations that seek to collaborate to bring about food system transformation in an area. FPNs have been proven to be a promising governance arrangement to sustain long-term multi-stakeholder engagement to interact on transformative food systems at a city-region level. The FPN will initially operate based on a collective understanding of the city-region food system, a shared vision for the urban food environment and jointly performed analysis of good practices. Informed by this knowledge base, FPNs will formulate an integrated food strategy to make healthy and sustainable food the easy choice for all. Networking activities will be organized to enrol more government actors, CSOs, private actors, higher education institutions and research organisations (T3.1), which will result in an increased FPN membership of at least 50% across all stakeholder categories.

Food Sustainability Tool: A FoodCLIC mapping tool co-created with stakeholders and tailored to each city-region’s context. The tool measures climate impact by assessing the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of food production and consumption patterns through the Carbon Footprint indicator and making use of the main land-cover categories according to EU COPERNICUS – 2018 Corinne Land Cover.

Initiatives to change urban food systems: Initiatives that produce changes to food environments in the cities and towns involved in the city-region, while also resulting in changes throughout the food system (e.g., the distribution channels, sites of production, etc.). They are similar to “real-life interventions”, which are initiatives to change urban food systems undertaken as part of the FoodCLIC project. They may be distinguished from a food policy if they are more trade-oriented instead of a clear integrated strategic perspective.

Living Lab: A virtual and physical spaces for members of the food policy networks in the city regions to understand the food system and co-design, implement, analyze and evaluate real-life interventions that aim to improve urban food environments through action learning.

Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP): In 2014, the Mayor of Milan decided to launch an international protocol aimed at tackling food-related issues at the urban level, to be adopted by as many world cities as possible. The Milan Urban Food Policy Pact was signed on the 15 October 2015 in Milan by more than 100 cities. <https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/>

Pilot City-region: Eight European city regions are involved to pilot FoodCLIC’s theory of change. These include: Area de Metropolitana de Barcelona, Spain; Berlin, Germany; Braşov Metropolitan Area, Romania; Budapest, Hungary; Aarhus, Denmark; Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal; Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam, Netherlands; and Plain of Lucca

Real-life intervention (RLI): Actions (implemented by FoodCLIC) that produce changes to food environments in the cities and towns involved, which result in changes throughout the food system (e.g., the distribution channels, sites of production, etc.). These actions may involve either first-time trials of a particular RLI in a city-region or the scaling-out of an on-going initiative at one location in the city-region to other locations in the city-region. The RLIs that FoodCLIC is seeking to implement and scale will allow city-regions to fill gaps in their knowledge and build the evidence-base for policy-making and planning to realize food system transformation.

Reflexive Monitoring and Dynamic Evaluation (RMDE) framework: The RMDE framework enables regular reflexive multi-actor monitoring to identify barriers to, and opportunities for, improving local food environments and transforming urban food systems.

Stakeholders: Persons, groups, or organisations that are (1) affected by the project, (2) interested in the project, and/or (3) able to affect the project.

Urban Agriculture and Food Systems (RUAF): RUAF is an international organisation that aims to accelerate food systems transformation for greater environmental, social, and economic sustainability, resilience, and equity in cities and city regions around the world. <https://ruaf.org/about/>

1. INTRODUCTION

In FoodCLIC, experimentation and action-learning are fundamental to the theory of change. Therefore, over the course of 24 months, Living Labs in eight city-regions work on more than thirty-five real-life interventions (RLIs)¹. These interventions, together with other WP3 activities, aim to catalyze food system transformation in two ways. First, they stimulate the collection of evidence for best practices and learnings about barriers for transformation. Second, they aim to directly influence transformations by changing the science-policy-practice interface (SPPI), as well as the realm of food related policy in each city-region.

To this end, monitoring and evaluation plays a key role in FoodCLIC. Throughout the project, Living Lab teams are supposed to assess learnings, processes, outcomes and impacts related to the SPPI, policy development and interventions in food environments. This is not only done after the interventions (ex-post), but also prior to (ex-ante) and during the interventions. In this way, insights collected through monitoring and evaluation help to iteratively shape the action-learning pathways that are explored by researchers and societal stakeholders. In that process, what is monitored and how, is determined not only by academic researchers, but in close collaboration with city-regional policymakers and societal changemakers.

To this end, the Reflexive Monitoring and Dynamic Evaluation (RMDE) framework presented here is developed as part of FoodCLIC task 1.3: Co-designing of a Food Sustainability Tool and Reflexive Monitoring and Dynamic Evaluation framework for the Living Labs. This deliverable, D1.4, serves as a guideline for the Living Lab teams. The RMDE framework is intended as a tool for transformation, that can be applied both within and beyond the project. The RMDE framework is tested through application by the Living Lab teams. A tested and updated version will be made available publicly as part of the FoodCLIC toolkit for city-regional food system transformation, which will become part of the CLEVERFOOD toolkit.

1.1 ROLES AND RESOURCES

Each Living Lab consists of a practice partner and a research partner. The research partners are responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of the RLIs. For each Living Lab, approximately one fulltime equivalent (1 FTE) is available for monitoring and evaluation over the course of the RLIs (22 person-months). Living Lab researchers have to determine how many resources, time and effort are allocated to the monitoring for each intervention. Ideally, this is done in close collaboration with the Living Lab coordinator and societal stakeholders. The coordinating parties in the Living Lab ideally have a facilitating role in the monitoring and evaluation, particularly during peak moments of data

¹ See FoodCLIC Deliverable 3.2 for a full overview of the RLIs.

collection, such as at baseline (~M21-M24), during reflexive learning sessions and at endline (~M45-M48).

Each Living Lab has financial resources available for the purpose of monitoring and evaluation. These resources are allocated to the research partner in each Living Lab. The resources include the means to buy presents or give compensation to participants in RLIs (€14,450). It is possible to use these means to compensate the approximately 250 participants involved in the monitoring of diets and health status. In addition, there is €15,000 available for additional data collection purposes, for example through organising focus group discussions.

1.2 GUIDE TO THE READER

In this document, we present the RMDE framework in the context of the FoodCLIC project. We do so by providing a brief overview of current challenges in monitoring (food) system transformation, particularly at city-regional scale (chapter 2). Then, we outline how the RMDE framework is connected to different objectives of the FoodCLIC project and to the theory of change (chapter 3). Finally, we provide a stepwise overview of the RMDE framework, namely as a set of core-indicators, and a set of context-specific indicators (chapter 4). These indicators and frameworks are accompanied by a set of tools to contextualise and shape locally relevant RMDE frameworks for each Living Lab (appendices). In chapter 5, the outline of when and how the RMDE framework needs to be applied is provided. We integrate the FoodCLIC guidelines on Implementing & learning from RLIs.

Chapter 4 and 5 give practical instructions to Living Lab researchers on how to set up monitoring plans, obtain insights relevant to the action-learning process and collect evidence on the impact of FoodCLIC in each city-region. Monitoring and evaluation efforts at baseline and during the interventions are intended to feed the reflexive learning cycles with evidence about challenges, barriers and opportunities for transformation. In combination with the endline assessment, an ex-post assessment of the overall impact can be made for each Living Lab. A graphic overview of the RMDE-framework is provided below.

Figure 1: Graphic overview of the RMDE framework.

2. MONITORING FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION

2.1 FOOD SYSTEMS AS COMPLEX SYSTEMS

Over the past decades, food systems have gravitated more towards the centre of attention for politicians, policymakers, researchers, and practitioners. Particularly in urban regions there has been growing attention for food policy and planning, oriented at the creation of more healthy and sustainable food environments and food systems. Initiatives such as the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP) have helped in placing food firmly on the urban agenda. FoodCLIC can be considered part of a range of projects commissioned by the European Commission that aim to explore how food systems can be transformed.

However, food systems are at the nexus of a range of sustainability challenges, ranging from health to sustainability and from social inclusion to transformational governance. Understanding these complex systems is one thing, trying to navigate a transformation is another. With a range of initiatives aiming to transform (aspects of) food systems, monitoring and evaluation is key in assessing what transformative action looks like and what outcomes and impacts are related to different actions. However, setting up monitoring and evaluation for city-regional food systems is challenging. Multiple attempts have been made, which all aim to deal with key challenges.

2.2 KEY CHALLENGES IN MONITORING & EVALUATION

For practitioners, researchers and policymakers, several tools are available that help to understand food systems and monitor change in key areas. Well-known city-regional tools include the monitoring framework tied to the MUFPP and the City-Regional Food System (CRFS) sustainability and resilience indicator framework (FAO, 2019; FAO & RUAFA, 2023). Global efforts on creating comprehensive insight into food systems on a national basis have been brought together at the Food System Dashboard. In 2021, after the UN Food System Summit, a group of authors released the Food System Countdown Initiative, a global tracker based on fifty indicators of the Food System Dashboard that together inform the state of national food systems in relation to the 2030 UN sustainable development goals (SDGs) (Fanzo et al., 2021). These frameworks are a valuable resource and a great step towards standardisation in the assessment of (city-regional) food systems (Sibbing et al., 2022). Moreover, they allow for an integrated approach towards food system assessment, coupling policy and practice to broad themes such as income security and government effectiveness.

There are, however, key challenges related to these frameworks. Sibbing et al. (2022) report that little is known about the adoption of the monitoring frameworks by city regions. In addition, they state that selecting indicators is challenging due to the number of options. Without a clear guideline on how to build a monitoring framework for a specific city-region and come to a robust and systemic set of indicators (and who to involve), monitoring and evaluation may focus on less transformative outcomes and low-hanging fruit. Finally, they observe that cities tend to focus on process-based indicators, as opposed to outcome and impact indicators (Sibbing et al., 2022).

An additional concern with these monitoring frameworks, is that they tend to focus on 'countable' or 'quantifiable' outcomes. These may help in communicating understandable effects, but they omit key developments in qualitative outcomes. Following the efforts of the Transformative Innovation Policy Consortium (TIPC), it becomes clear that 'transformative outcomes' of policy experiments often hinge on more qualitative outcomes, such as 'disrupting policy frameworks and governance arrangements' (Molas-Gallart et al., 2021).

In tandem with these international efforts, several cities, food networks and researchers have set out to create their own food system monitoring frameworks. Examples of these include the indicator sets used by the city of [New York](#) to track progress as part of their Food Forward policy. In San Diego, the Food System Alliance tracks progress on its goals via a comprehensive monitoring [dashboard](#). These networks can address local issues, through contextualised monitoring practices. Consequently, there is a lot of diversity between different monitoring approaches, complicating the translocal comparability of challenges, barriers, and best practices between FoodCLIC city-regions and beyond.

In both the international and local efforts, an important question is related to who decides what to monitor. Sibbing et al., (2022) refer to Stone (2011, p.188): *"Measures imply a need for action, because we don't measure things except when we want to change them or change our behaviour in response to them. To call for a measurement or survey of something is to take the first step in promoting change"*. However, who makes the call, is of great importance to whose transformation is acted upon in changing city-regional food systems.

A practical limitation to the above is the fact that data availability at city-regional scale may be low. Bringing together existing data at this new scale may lead to new insights but may also lead to the strengthening of existing patterns if no new insights are gained. On the contrary, collecting new data may be costly and difficult to institutionalise. Monitoring efforts must weigh which insights benefit whom (Moragues-Faus, 2020).

These challenges are persistent. For one, data gaps are not easily solved. In addition, it requires a learning approach to find out in what way city-regional food systems are desired to transform. A static collection of indicators is not well suited to support this learning approach. As the RLIs in FoodCLIC experiment for transformation, it is important to find ways to deal with the challenges above. In the next chapter, the purpose and the approach of monitoring in FoodCLIC are outlined.

3. MONITORING IN FOODCLIC

In FoodCLIC, monitoring is tightly weaved through the project. To understand how the monitoring and evaluation framework is built up, the three core objectives of FoodCLIC are outlined in section 3.1. Section 3.2 guides the reader past two principles in the FoodCLIC Theory of Change that are intended to take up some of the key challenges presented in chapter 2: action-learning and transdisciplinary research. In section 3.3, a synthesis is provided, of how the FoodCLIC Reflexive Monitoring and Dynamic Evaluation (RMDE) framework, aims to work as a tool for transformation.

3.1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

There are three interrelated objectives central to the project and its (multilevel) theory of change (see Figure 1):

- (1) Strengthening science-policy-practice interfaces (SPPIs);
- (2) Building evidence for more healthy and sustainable food environments and food systems;
- (3) Stimulate the creation of evidence-informed, food sensitive policies and planning frameworks.

Figure 2: FoodCLIC's architecture and Theory of Change (DoA Part B, p.6)

OBJECTIVE 1: STRENGTHENING SPPI

Following the FoodCLIC theory of change, the first objective is fundamental to the other two. At the core of the Living Lab in each city-region, is the aim to strengthen the connection between researchers, policymakers, entrepreneurs, and practitioners that work on food (systems). In the Living Lab, the focus lies on strengthening food policy networks (FPNs), that, when designed well, stimulate interaction at the interface of these different stakeholder groups. These FPNs can take up a role as systemic transition intermediaries (Calancie et al., 2018; den Boer et al., 2023). For this, they are required to embody transformative knowledge, operate under transformative leadership and allow space for experimentation and foster an inclusive council climate (e.g. include space for quadruple helix representation, food deprived and vulnerable groups and women). How FPNs develop and to what extent they (can) act as systemic transition intermediaries in each Living Lab needs to be monitored throughout the action phase of FoodCLIC. To this end, all Living Lab teams have gathered insight into the (potential) FPNs in their respective city-regions, as part of task 2.4. To see whether the SPPI actually strengthens during the action phase of FoodCLIC, a baseline assessment is taken prior to the start of the RLIs (ex-ante). Towards the end of the project, after two years of RLI activities, an endline assessment is taken (ex-post). The monitoring that needs to take place for this objective, is focused on changes in processes and in 'transformative outcomes' (Molas-Gallart et al., 2021).

OBJECTIVE 2: BUILDING EVIDENCE

The second objective in FoodCLIC is centred around experimentation for transformation. Through experiments (RLIs), evidence will be generated for best practices in food system transformation, as well as on obstacles and barriers, and how to overcome them. The experiments conducted in each Living Lab depend on the context of the city-region. These experiments ideally respond to the initial situation. To indicate change generated by the RLIs, outcome indicators are required to be compared between baseline and endline. However, to assess learning of the RLIs, process-based indicators should focus on developments throughout the application period of the interventions as well (~M21-M48).

OBJECTIVE 3: POLICIES & PLANNING

The third objective is primarily tied to the development of policies and planning frameworks in the FoodCLIC pilot city-regions. However, changes in policy and planning take time and are difficult to attribute to singular experiments, mainly due to their long development time. For this reason, a secondary focus is taken on the learning among relevant policymakers. Once again, for this objective, outcome indicators that compare the situation at baseline and endline, as well as process-based indicators are required. The latter type require the Living Lab teams to track learning throughout the action phase of FoodCLIC. Who and what to keep track of may differ in each city-region. Task 2.3 has provided a first insight into the relevant policies and planning frameworks in each city-region.

As part of the Theory of Change in FoodCLIC, the three objectives form an integrated whole. Essentially, for food system transformation to succeed, receptive and active policymakers must be supplied with socially robust evidence about desired changes to food environments and food systems. Likewise, experimentation by practitioners hopefully generates policy-relevant evidence, based upon accurate learning needs. This iterative exchange is facilitated, but also mediated through strengthened and inclusive SPPIs (figure 1).

3.2 THEORY OF CHANGE

ACTION-LEARNING

In each Living Lab, FoodCLIC partners aim to start a process of action-learning. First, the Living Lab teams undertake situated actions towards local objectives, informed by the systemic lens provided by the project. This action consists of activities in FoodCLIC Work Package 3. This includes the strengthening of FPNs (Task 3.1), the design and execution of RLLs (Task 3.4), and the development of a local Community of Practice for policymakers (Task 3.3). Second, the Living Lab teams stimulate reflexive learning at the science-policy-practice interface.

The combination of these activities should enable the Living Lab teams to start an action-learning spiral, in which design – action – observation – reflection – redesign cycles help stakeholders to not only understand what actions help in creating systemic change, but to also actively take away obstacles for success and redesign actions into more successful ones (see figure 3). Once this dynamic can be fostered, the Living Lab teams start spiralling towards a desired dynamic target.

Figure 3: Action-learning spiral

The action-learning approach fosters reflexive learning. This helps Living Lab teams to engage with (systemic) obstacles encountered in the real-life interventions. However, the direction in which action-learning takes place and consequentially, which obstacles are encountered and overcome, depends on who's questions and objectives are central to the experiment. In FoodCLIC, this process is embedded in a transdisciplinary 'coalition' of societal stakeholders, policymakers and researchers.

TRANSDISCIPLINARY SOURCES OF INDICATORS

Action-learning helps to create a process that is reflexive. But for whom and about what? To ensure a more democratic and successful RLI, Living Lab teams are stimulated to work in coalitions consisting of at least three types of stakeholders: social society, policymakers, and researchers. Even when indicators are selected democratically, it is common for 'means' to become 'ends'. It is vital to realize that the role of monitoring is pivotal in working out in which direction interventions could and should spiral. To prevent an unbalanced set of indicators to steer the process, three types of indicators are combined in each intervention: (1) 'policy relevant indicators' collect evidence to help to answer questions of local policymakers; (2) 'socially robust meaningful measures' relate to what societal stakeholder value in food system transformation; and (3) 'systemic indicators' aim to connect intervention-specific insights to city-regional food system challenges. Each type of indicator is elaborated below.

Policy relevant indicators

Fundamental to the experimentation in FoodCLIC, is that it fosters the creation of evidence-informed and integrated food sensitive policies (objective 3). The way in which this is realized in each Living Lab depends on the local challenges and opportunities to design/create food-sensitive policy and planning frameworks. To generate insightful evidence and transformative knowledge, the questions of local policymakers during action-reflection cycles give direction to the policy-relevant objectives for each RLI. Around these objectives, policy-relevant indicators can be formulated, that contribute to the learning amongst this stakeholder group and to foster the creation of more food sensitive policies and planning frameworks. In each Living Lab, the number and type of policymakers may differ. The way in which these policymakers engage with the evidence generated during the action phases may also differ. FoodCLIC stimulates the creation of a Community of Practice for policymakers, that meets in tandem with the reflexive learning sessions (before, during or after). However, policymakers can, where possible, also be directly involved in interventions, to create shorter feedback loops between (policy) obstacles and experimental learning.

Socially robust meaningful measures

The experimentation for transformation in FoodCLIC is grounded in the notion that food system transformation should lead to improved access to healthy and sustainable food for everyone, meaning that particular attention is devoted to the needs of relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups in the design, execution, and redesign of interventions. To stimulate the integration of experiential knowledge from people who find themselves in a disempowering position in relation to the current food system, representatives of (organisations who work with) relatively food-deprived and/or vulnerable groups are co-designing interventions in FoodCLIC. More generally, the Living Lab is constructed with the purpose to involve the experience, insight and knowledge from local communities and food changemakers in each city-region, namely because of their key-insight into current food system dynamics and their effects on the local communities of interest. The interventions that are shaped during co-design reflect action on objectives that are supported by these communities. To understand what change towards these objectives should look like, and how

it should be monitored, the perspectives of these stakeholders should be incorporated to create socially robust indicators, or 'meaningful measures' for change. Essentially, these indicators should help formulate an answer to the question: 'And how can we see that this [objective] has changed'?

Systemic indicators

Finally, the aim of FoodCLIC is to take a systems approach towards transformation in each of the Living Labs requires a thorough understanding of the city-regional food system. The mapping & gapping phase (work package 2) allowed for the identification of opportunities for transformation, based upon the CLIC framework. For the interventions to stay on track in working on systemic transformation, it is necessary to maintain the connection between the CRFS's overarching characteristics and specific obstacles, as well as opportunities, in relation to the intervention. In other words, what objective does the intervention serve from a system transformation point of view. The different 'strategic approaches' from Training 4 (e.g. disruptive, narrative, prefigurative, etc.), which took place as part of work package 1 (task 1.4), point towards this overarching objective. Interventions may, for example, contribute to deepening understanding of a mechanism, broadening the application of a particular tool or model, or aim to change the narrative around an aspect of the food system. This category of indicators may also be fed by the CLIC framework as ultimately, it revolves around how we expect to change the system, based upon the theory of change.

3.3 APPROACH OF REFLEXIVE MONITORING AND DYNAMIC EVALUATION

A more dynamic and reflexive approach for monitoring and evaluation, helps the Living Lab teams in dealing with the challenges identified in the previous chapter. For Living Lab researchers in FoodCLIC, it is important to understand that monitoring serves a dual purpose. On the one hand, researchers should monitor progress towards clearly defined objectives, whereby the objectives and the associated indicators should be informed by policy-relevant, socially robust and systemic perspectives. This requires a dynamic and contextualised approach. On the other hand, monitoring is intended to avoid tunnel vision and prevent indicators from becoming objectives themselves, identify obstacles in time and create awareness of connections and opportunities. This requires a highly reflexive approach. Reflexive monitoring allows a monitor to put *"the prevailing values and institutional settings up for discussion"* (van Mierlo et al., 2010, p.36). In sum:

1. Assess impact for different stakeholders through policy-relevant, socially robust and systemic indicators.
2. Avoiding tunnel vision, by reflexively engaging with indicators, and underlying values, actively changing and steering towards opportunities over the horizon.

The design of FoodCLIC's activities in the context of the Living Lab as an action-learning spiral, with dedicated action-reflection cycles, enables the FoodCLIC Living Lab teams to *feed data and learnings*

back into the process. Thereby, (re)designed action starts to reflexively embody the collective learning process of FoodCLIC and shape into more transformative interventions.

A key tool used in FoodCLIC to monitor learning as part of the action-learning spiral, is the Dynamic Learning Agenda (DLA) (van Mierlo et al., 2010). This tool is used in FoodCLIC to take stock of key learning questions, that help to identify barriers and obstacles to transformation. By applying the DLA consistently over the course of the interventions, shifts in perceived obstacles, as well as key learnings, become visible. The application of the DLA is closely related to the six-monthly reflexive learning sessions. Internal [guidelines](#) are available for Living Lab teams on how to apply the DLA (publicly available after August 2024 – D1.6).

4. THE REFLEXIVE MONITORING AND DYNAMIC EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

The RMDE framework is a tool that enables Living Lab researchers to assess (1) the transformative outcomes of the Living Lab, (2) the specific outcomes and impacts of interventions, and (3) the relation between the experiments for transformation and systemic change. To this end, the framework is built up out of two main components (Figure 3). First, to monitor transformative outcomes and changes in processes in relation to the Living Lab, a set of general **core-indicators** has been created centrally, that is to be applied by all Living Lab researchers, at the onset (baseline study) and at the end (endline study) of the RLIs' implementation. This helps to track progress over time, as well as compare Living Labs translocally. Second, each local real-life intervention has a specific contribution in terms of action and learning towards food system transformation. To assess this contribution, a specific set of indicators is composed by the Living Lab researchers, we refer to these sets as **context-specific indicators**. These indicators cover a wide range of topics, due to the broad range of activities in the RLIs. For each intervention, a specific set is created. Across the interventions, there is a minimum requirement for health & nutrition monitoring, while other types of indicators are created based upon the needs of different stakeholders. Living Lab researchers can compose a monitoring plan, including three types of indicators, namely standardised health & nutrition indicators, free-choice sustainability indicators and other policy-relevant, socially robust or systemic indicators.

4.1 CORE INDICATORS

The core indicator set of FoodCLIC can be used to track progress towards the three overarching project objectives. The core-indicators consist of four themes (table 2). The core-indicators are supposed to be **assessed at the start of the intervention period and towards the end of the project**. Most of the indicators are not directly related to activities in the RLIs. Therefore, *the timeline for their assessment is not strictly coupled to the start and end of the RLIs*. However, the interventions are at the heart of the project. For this reason, most changes are expected to take place around the period that the RLIs are being implemented. Hence, it is wise to conduct a baseline as early as possible. Throughout the period of experimentation in RLIs, there is no intermittent reporting for the Living Lab teams. We strongly advice researchers to collect data well before a reflection cycle, to allow time for analysis and make the most of the feedback mechanism. This applies to contextual indicators, but also to the core-indicators, as these may point to processes relevant for policymakers and food policy networks (for a full overview of a suggested timeline, check the researchers' to do list: figure 4).

Table 2: The four themes of the core indicators

SYSTEM THINKING: THE CLIC-FRAMEWORK	This theme addresses the extent to which evidence generation occurs in an integrative and systemic manner, by using the CLIC framework to highlight system aspects that require attention in city-regional food system transformation.
ACTION-LEARNING APPROACH	In this theme, indicators point towards the use and usefulness of action-learning as a methodological approach in the Living Labs.
SCIENCE-POLICY-PRACTICE INTERFACE	Indicators in this theme help the Living Lab teams to evaluate the status of the science-policy-practice interface and monitor progress in its strengthening and integration. Specific attention is given to the role of Food Policy Networks, and their capacity to act as a systemic transition intermediary.
POLICY & PLANNING DEVELOPMENT	This theme addresses the status of policy and planning prior to, during and after the action-learning phase in FoodCLIC. It mainly contains indicators that point towards the transformative outcomes in policy and planning development.

For each of the themes, several objectives and desired outcomes are provided, as well as more specific indicators that are to be monitored by the Living Lab researchers. **While some of these indicators are specific, the way the Living Lab researchers may collect the required insights may differ.** Information can be drawn from FoodCLIC activities and documentation, but may also rely

upon additional interviews, participant observation, desk research or other research activities. The core-indicators are not prescriptive in this sense.

It is equally important to realize, that the collection of these insights is a learning activity in itself. In different contexts, indicators may be more or less relevant, and this is indicative of relevant local dynamics. Therefore, it is possible for Living Lab researchers to change an indicator from quantitative to qualitative, or the other way around. Here, it is very helpful for other Living Lab researchers if the choice can be motivated. Over the course of the interventions, additional insights may lead the Living Lab researchers across the project to adopt additional indicators, that are added to the endline. For these indicators, it is always important to make sure that some type of baseline can be established (in hindsight, if the data is available), so that the effect of FoodCLIC's activities on these indicators may be better understood.

While the current set of core-indicators is based on relevant experience and rooted in existing work, it is not perfect, nor finalised. Over the course of the coming two years, we aim to gather insights through the core-indicators, but also about the core-indicators. It is valuable to find out what works and what does not and how this may differ per context. This results in a tried and tested list of core-indicators for transformative outcomes of city-regional food systems, that FoodCLIC can make available as a tool for transformation.

The core indicators themselves are based on the impact-section of FoodCLIC and can be found in Table 3. In addition, the work of the TIP consortium has been used to determine indicators that point towards transformative outcomes of the Living Lab activities (Molas-Gallart et al., 2021). The model used to structure the indicators is based on the CRFS sustainability indicator framework (Carey et al., n.d.). Inspiration has also been drawn from the Food System Countdown Initiative (Fanzo et al.,

To do list for Living Lab researchers		
To do	Description	Timeline
Review indicators	For each indicator, check whether and how it fits your local context. How does it help you and others build an understanding of the potential transformative outcomes of the Living Lab?	May/June 2024
Determine methods	For each indicator, see how information can best be collected. Take into account the suggestions provided and motivate why you should take a different approach in your Living Lab.	June 2024
Answer what you know	Based upon the mapping & gapping or co-design, it may be possible to already fill out particular indicators.	June 2024
Organise & start additional data collection	Fill out the remaining indicators through interviews, desk research, focus groups, participant observation or other approaches.	June - September 2024

Figure 4: Core indicator to do list for Living Lab researchers

2021), as well as from a reflexive monitoring framework developed by DRIFT for the project 'Rotterdam de Boer op' (de Pater, pers. comm., unpublished). The core indicators fall into four distinct categories (Table 2), that reflect the FoodCLIC theory of change. For each theme, multiple objectives are specified. The desired direction of travel is indicated in the outcome category and, to track progress, specific indicators have been formulated. For each indicator, a suggested data source is outlined. In addition, a reflection column is added, in which Living Lab teams' experience with the indicators will be addressed.

Table 3: Overview of the core-indicators of the RMDE framework

	Objectives	Outcome	Key issues to measure	Possible core-indicator	Suggested data sources
FoodCLIC takes systems approach towards transformation For experiments to contribute to food system transformation, an integrated approach towards the food system is required. The CLIC-framework provides a means to analyse the transformative capacity of interventions, both at the level of the food environment as well as at the food system.					
1	Co-benefits: Realizing sustainability co-benefits: creating synergies and avoiding trade-offs between environmental, social and economic sustainability.	Create synergistic solutions for sustainability challenges	Synergies	% of RLIs that create synergies between 3 out of 3 sustainability co-benefits at baseline and endline	Analysis of (re-designed) action and learning plans of FoodCLIC interventions
2				Description of interventions that realize sustainability co-benefits	Analysis of (re-designed) action and learning plans/interviews with coordinators/ stakeholders RLIs
3		Avoiding trade-offs in interventions	Trade-offs	Trade-offs between sustainability co-benefits and ways in which they have been addressed in reflexive-learning cycles	Analysis of (re-designed) action and learning plans of FoodCLIC interventions; interview with coordinators/co-coordinators of interventions.
4	Linkages: Strengthening urban-rural linkages in form of positive spatial, socio-cultural, economic and environmental relations between "urban" and "rural".	Adoption of food system approach: incl. perspectives from food production (and associated inputs) through to food consumption and waste	Systemic integration	% of interventions targeting change in both food production and consumption	Analysis of (re-designed) action and learning plans of FoodCLIC interventions; interview with coordinators/co-coordinators of RLIs
5		Foster positive flows between urban and rural areas	Urban-rural integration	% of interventions that include activities in both urban and rural areas	Analysis of (re-designed) action and learning plans of FoodCLIC interventions
6			Urban-rural relations	# of participants from urban and rural communities	Count participants during workshops, follow up questions
7			Best practices that lead to strengthened linkages	Analysis of (re-designed) action and learning plans of FoodCLIC interventions	
8	Inclusion: The inclusion of systemically excluded stakeholders into the design and development of future food systems	There is equitable participation and representation in system understanding, visioning, strategizing, co-design	Citizen participation	% of participants from helix pillar: citizens	Documentation from system understanding/ visioning/strategizing
9				% of participants (directly representing) relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups during system understanding - co-design.	Documentation on co-design
10				% of female participants (gender balance)	Documentation on co-design
11			Participation of relatively food deprived and/or vulnerable groups	Barriers reported to the involvement of relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups	Documentation on co-design
12				Best practices applied to improve the involvement of relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups in interventions	Documentation on co-design
13				Equitable participation in action-learning	% of indicators in interventions informed by and answering to requests of citizen

		developed by co-researchers, citizens and changemakers		stakeholders (characterised as socially robust meaningful measures)	
14		Food deprived and vulnerable groups are involved in design, implementation, monitoring and re-design		% of interventions that involve food-deprived and vulnerable groups in design; implementation; monitoring and re-design	Reflexive learning sessions (focus groups)
15				Barriers reported to involvement of relatively food-deprived and vulnerable groups	Reflexive learning sessions (focus groups)
16				Best practices applied to improve the involvement of relatively food-deprived and vulnerable groups in interventions	Reflexive learning sessions (focus groups)
17		Explicit food justice/right to food approach is taken towards food system transformation		Presence of explicit food (&) justice framework and approach in interventions	Analysis of vision, strategy and co-design documentation
18	Connectivities: Fostering an integrated approach towards food and its relationships with health, wellbeing and the environment	Stimulate the integration of different policy domains on the topic of food.	Policy domains involved in food (sensitive) policy	# of different policy domains contributing to the drafting of food policy	Interview with policymakers on food policy
19				# of departments/domains that draft food sensitive policy	Interviews with policymakers from diverse domains
20		Incorporate food as topic in urban planning procedures	Urban planning procedures	In what way is food a topic considered in urban planning procedures?	Interviews with urban planners
21		Connect food to range of integrated topics, such as health, energy, water use	Connectivity	Which local topics of concern (e.g., health gaps, climate change, farming/food security) are actively connected to food?	Observation of FPN activities, analysis of policy documents where food is mentioned
Learning in action in the living lab: Across the FoodCLIC living labs, a learning-in-action approach is taken towards food system transformation.					
22	Identify, explicate and engage with obstacles for food system transformation, to identify contextual and general best practices	Local obstacles for transformative action in interventions are identified and explicated	Obstacles for transformation	Structure is in place to continuously identify obstacles to transformation	DLA
23		Using a learning-in-action approach to overcome obstacles for transformative action		# of policy-relevant questions resolved during FoodCLIC interventions	DLA reporting template; monitoring plan of each RLI
24		Best practices in dealing with obstacles are identified and shared		Description of best practices applied to deal with obstacles met during implementation of RLIs	Interviews with stakeholders in RLIs, Living Lab coordinators and involved policymakers
25	Deepen, broaden and anchor interventions, to continuously	In interventions, space is made to deepen understanding of transformative capacity of actions	Deepening	Learning amongst policymakers, citizens and researchers about transformative capacity of RLIs	Interviews, DLA
26			Broadening	# of replications of (successful) concepts	

27	stimulate learning-in-action	Interventions are broadened, replicated and scaled up/out		Increase in involvement/growth of interventions	Track involvement over reflexive-learning cycles. Count participation in interventions
28		Interventions are embedded in institutions	Anchoring	Structural involvement of policymakers	Evaluation of RLIs
29				Increased financial security of RLI through securing of subsidies, uptake in government programmes or development of sustainable business models	
30	Design - act - observe - reflect - re-design	Interventions help to start spiralling towards a desired future, by fostering learning through action and re-applying learnings in action.	Action-learning spiral	Apply reflexive learning sessions to redesign interventions	
31				# of learnings explicitly applied in re-design	Analysis of (re-designed) action and learning plans of FoodCLIC interventions
32				Sense of progress with key stakeholders	Interview with stakeholders: do you feel that you have moved forward? How?
Strengthening the science-policy-practice interface , to facilitate knowledge exchange between all relevant stakeholders to food system transformation and strengthen FPNs to act as systemic transition intermediaries.					
33	Increase the membership and diversity of FPNs	FPNs have increased active membership (+50%) and diversity	Membership	% growth in active membership with FPNs	What constitutes a member in different FPNs is flexible – contextual application of what this term means is a learning for the FPN and the LL-team.
34				(Direct) representation of relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups in FPNs.	Qualitative measure (can be different in every context) of executive agendas, visions, actual meetings, events, etc.
35			Diversity	Diversity of stakeholders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quadruple helix - Gender - Socio-economic status 	It is possible to take measure of diversity (Shannon-index) to indicate how structurally diverse network is based upon diversity across the quadruple helix, or with respect to the gender balance and the inclusion of food deprived and vulnerable groups.
36	Increase the transformative capacity of FPNs	FPNs apply transformative leadership: actively steering towards food system transformation	Leadership	Systemic action orientation of FPN	Is there an executive agenda, are there action lines along which action is taken?
37		FPNs are endorsed institutionally in city-region	Institutional endorsement	# of FPNs newly initiated/institutionalised.	Interviews/desk research
38				Involvement of policymakers in FPN	Interviews with policymakers and FPN coordinators
39				Structural budget for FPN activities present	Documentation or interviews.
40		Transformative knowledge about food system is internalized in FPNs		Baseline insight into food system and food environments	Reports on RLIs
41	FPNs maintain Living Lab and harvest learnings.			Observation/interviews	

42		Capacity development in FPN members		FPN members are capable of applying a systems approach in actions.	Interviews/participatory observation, document analysis: executive agendas can give a good overview of how systemic an FPN approaches the food system.
43		Inclusive council climate		Diversity of FPN core-group <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quadruple helix - Gender - Socio-economic status 	Interviews/participatory observation; with specific attention for diversity across the quadruple helix, the gender balance and the inclusion of food deprived and vulnerable groups.
44				Increased experience of trust and sense of belonging with FPN members	Interviews/participatory observation
45		Member empowerment	Participation	Members feel ownership over FPN and space to make decisions	Interviews/participatory observation
46		Increase knowledge development on food system transformation	Existence of city-regional network of higher education/ research organisations with research agenda on food system transformation	Research	# of HEIs/ROs working on research for food system (transformation)
47	# of spaces in which HEIs/ROs collaborate/exchange knowledge on food system (transformation)				Interviews/desk research
Shaping integrated and evidence-informed policy & planning					
48	Increase prevalence and quality of food (sensitive) policies in city-region	Municipalities have drafted integrated food policies, such as visions or strategies.	Food policy	% of population in city-region living in cities/municipalities that are signatories to MUFPP	Desk research
49				% of population in the city-region living in cities/municipalities that have food vision/strategy	Desk research
50		Food policies have increased in depth and breadth (CLIC) and effectiveness		Presence of executive agenda coupled to food policy	Desk research + interviews with relevant local policymakers.
51				Budget allocated to food policy	Desk research + interviews with relevant local policymakers.
52	Reflexive & evidence-informed policymaking	Food policies and planning frameworks are designed together with societal stakeholders	Policy co-creation	Describe if and how input from quadruple helix stakeholders is used in the drafting of new food policies	Interviews with policymakers and said to be involved societal stakeholders
53		Food policies and planning frameworks incorporate lessons from relevant experiments	Evidence-informed policies	Describe if and how lessons and best practices from FoodCLIC or other relevant experiments are included in new food policies	Interviews with relevant policymakers
54		Food policies are reflexively evaluated after a period	Reflexive evaluation	Describe if and how food policies are (scheduled to be) evaluated and whether results feed into new food policy	Interviews with relevant policymakers

4.2 CONTEXT-SPECIFIC INDICATORS

At the cornerstone of the Living Labs are the RLIs. RLIs aim to contribute to food system transformation in each city-region by providing lessons learned and best practices, through experiments for transformation around strategic challenges and (local) obstacles. The logic behind each RLI is situated in the context of the city-regional food system and the Living Lab itself. This situatedness requires monitoring to be contextualised. However, in FoodCLIC, there is a wish to foster translocal learning as well. During the project, this learning should help to improve the transformative capacity of interventions in other Living Labs. Beyond FoodCLIC, the best practices that are collected should be translatable to other city-regions.

To strike a balance between comparability and contextualisation, a method is proposed to bring together a good set of indicators for each intervention. This method is built on important requirements for the RMDE-framework:

For all interventions in a Living Lab combined:

1. The health and diet of approximately 250 participants (approx. 80% from relatively food deprived and/or vulnerable groups and 50% female) is monitored from baseline to endline.

For any specific real-life intervention:

2. Indicators combine a mixed-methods approach (both quantitative and qualitative). This ensures that the broad effects of each intervention on the CRFS are best captured, understood and represented;
3. Indicators contribute to insights that are deemed policy-relevant, socially robust and systemic (see also section 5.3.2).

Based upon these conditions, we emphasize that what is monitored for each intervention, is primarily determined locally. The RMDE-framework does not prescribe indicators at the intervention level. However, the Living Lab researchers should ensure that for the sum of interventions, indicators meet condition 1. To see that conditions 2 and 3 are met, the researchers are advised to work out monitoring plans for each intervention. In these monitoring plans, indicators can be tied to specific objectives for each intervention (appendix B). In addition, sampling plans can be taken up for nutrition and health monitoring.

In the next sections, the different types of context-specific indicators are explained in detail. These instructions are directed at the Living Lab researchers and contain guidance and the occasional template. However, it is important to reiterate that the monitoring plans for each intervention are ideally designed together with participants. Participating citizens, entrepreneurs and policymakers should be asked to think about how they would expect to see a certain desired change to take place.

This information should ideally feed the monitoring plans. The structure provided there, is merely in place to support the researcher in covering all the topics that may be relevant during that process.

MONITORING HEALTH AND NUTRITION

Health, nutrition, and diets are an integral aspect of food system transformation.² Current food systems are responsible for unhealthy food environments and create to health inequalities. In FoodCLIC, the overarching vision for a future food system revolves partly around the capacity to create food environments that positively relate to health through diets and nutrition. Therefore, RLIs should contribute to improved links between health, nutrition, and diets, through more healthy food environments. To monitor whether and how interventions manage to positively influence this relationship, a basic understanding of health, food (in)security and dietary quality is collected by all living labs.

The methods that are applied to determine participants health, food (in)security and dietary quality are highly standardised. This facilitates comparability over time, between interventions and between Living Labs. In addition, using highly standardised and validated tools and questionnaires help Living Lab (co-)researchers to understand what it is exactly that they measure and what the collected data does and does not reflect. For the RMDE-framework, it is important that such robust methods are chosen, while the methodology remains accessible in use for researchers from diverse backgrounds. Particularly in the case of nutrition science, gathering insights into someone's health and diet is complex and is prone to bias. In the selection of the current methods, the burden for participants in the research has been carefully weighed against the scientific and societal benefit of the data collected.

Example of health and nutrition monitoring in Amsterdam city region

"In Amsterdam Noord, informal neighbourhood food initiatives (including food banks and neighbourhood cooks) provide food for their relatively food deprived neighbours. Currently, they largely rely on waste streams (e.g. from supermarkets) and are dependent on financial subsidies from the Amsterdam municipality.

Little is known about the size, food security status, and health of the target population. The initiatives all aim to contribute to more sustainable food consumption and more equal access to good food in the neighbourhood. This is part of their reason for existence. To foster a more healthy and sustainable model, the initiatives investigate the long-term opportunities for a food hub in Noord, together with FoodCLIC.

As part of this journey, it is important to show how these neighbourhood food initiatives can contribute to improved access to healthy and sustainable food for relatively food deprived residents. Therefore, we aim to monitor the diet quality, health and food security of participants, the composition and source of food aid, recipes used by cooks and the lived experience of what these initiatives mean for food deprived residents."

² More information on how to work with the questionnaires for health and nutrition monitoring can be found in Appendix A

All Living Lab teams will collect data using three questionnaires, through interviews between a researcher and a respondent. An overview of these questionnaires, their general characteristics and the potential indicators that can be determined based upon these is given in Table 5. Based upon these data, it is expected that general patterns and relations between health, food security and nutrition can be shown for the sampled populations. In addition, comparisons between baseline and endline can indicate changes in population level diet quality, as well as health and food security.

Many of the Living Labs may be interested to collect additional health data, that can be coupled to the standard questionnaire. In addition to general questions about the sampled population (e.g. gender, age, etc.) that can be used to stratify the sample, it is possible to add questionnaires for food and or health literacy, or to expand the dietary data collection with food diaries or food frequency questionnaires.

The application of these questionnaires in each Living Lab requires the Living Lab teams to prepare adequate translations and adapt the sentinel foods in the DQQ where possible, using the strategies provided by the questionnaire’s developers. A detailed description for these adaptations can be found in appendix 2 (health questionnaires).

Considering the comparability of the data, it is vital for the Living Labs to outline how the responses have been collected, how the sample has been determined and what the sample is representative of. In addition, the translated questionnaires, as well as the potential adaptations in sentinel foods have to be cross-checked prior to application with health experts in the FoodCLIC consortium. Lastly, a common data collection sheet will be created, where the Living Lab teams can deposit the anonymised data for analysis and cross-comparison.

Table 5: Overview of questionnaires, their general characteristics and the potential indicators

QUESTIONNAIRE	SOURCE	DESCRIPTION	INDICATOR
Self-perceived general health	European Health Interview Survey (or SF-36)	1-item questionnaire – participant is asked to rate their self-perceived health on a likert scale (1-5)	Self-perceived general health is reliable indicator for actual health
Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)	FAO, Validation study: Cafiero, Viviani & Nord (2019)	8-item questionnaire (max. 5 minutes) – inquires about different levels of experienced food insecurity. Can be administered at household or individual level. In FoodCLIC	Measure of experienced food insecurity

		individual level seems to be most appropriate approach	
Dietary Quality Questionnaire	Dietquality.org Herforth, et al., 2020.	29-item questionnaire (max 5 minutes) – lists country-specific sentinel foods for all important food groups. Respondents indicate which food groups they have consumed in previous 24-hours	This questionnaire enables calculation of Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women (MDD-W), and other population level indicators on diet quality, such as All-5 score, NCD-protect and NCD-risk score ³

MONITORING ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS

City-regional food systems have significant environmental effects, that are often related to production methods, as this is where the largest claim on land is made in the food supply chain. However, food production cannot be viewed separately from food processing, sale and consumption. As FoodCLIC operates in food environments, partly because this is the space in which consumption and production meet, the environmental effects of city-regional food systems require a strong focus to understand the potential sustainability of experiments in RLIs.

Several frameworks exist that aim to categorize the environmental effects of food systems. The planetary boundaries provide a useful starting point. Rockström et al. (2020) have estimated which planetary boundaries are transgressed by global food systems. In particular, biosphere integrity (genetic diversity) and biogeochemical flows (Phosphorous and Nitrogen cycle), show up as transgressed globally. In addition, greenhouse gas emissions, cropland use and freshwater use are transgressed as well. For four boundaries, the contribution is uncertain, but the authors expect that for ocean acidification and novel entities, there will certainly be an important contribution (Rockström et al., 2020).

³ For European countries, including the countries participating in FoodCLIC, specific data for women and relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups are lacking. The DQQ is specifically developed to collect these data in low-resource settings and is therefore highly suitable to the focus of the RLIs.

FOOD SUSTAINABILITY TOOL

FoodCLIC will use the specifically developed Food Sustainability Tool (FST) to assess the long-term effect of certain interventions on food systems' environmental sustainability. However, as reported by the authors of the global Food System Countdown Initiative (FSCI), data availability is a key barrier in monitoring food systems' contributions to several environmental sustainability outcomes (Fanzo et al., 2021). As a consequence, the FST focuses on greenhouse gas emissions, as well-developed methods exist, and data is reasonably available for the assessment of greenhouse gas emissions based upon food production and consumption.

The FST allows the Living Lab researchers to monitor and model the long-term effect of RLIs that target one of three topics, namely (1) food waste reduction, (2) changes in dietary patterns or (3) reduction in food mileage (e.g. increased consumption of local food). The modelling of CO₂-equivalent emissions is possible based on coarse or more fine-grained data that is to be collected by Living Lab researchers in the respective RLIs. The data that is required for these different levels of precision will be communicated by CMCC as part of the FST, which will be available from August 2024. In preparation for this, Living Lab researchers that are interested to apply this type of monitoring for their interventions, can work together with consortium partner CMCC in fine-tuning the data collection possibilities and requirements.

ADDITIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS

While city-regional estimates of CO₂-equivalent food system emissions are a top-priority for understanding the environmental effects, there are additional key priorities. As mentioned, biodiversity loss and biogeochemical flows are key aspects to consider in food systems. Experiments for transformation should not overlook these aspects. However, monitoring biodiversity loss, and changes in planetary or local biogeochemical flows is highly complex. Local developments may significantly influence system dynamics and the other way around. In many cases, there seem to be trade-offs between environmental effects. The intensification of food production may lead to more efficient land-use globally, but may affect biodiversity locally through increased use of chemical fertilizer, water or pesticides.

In table 6, an overview of the indicators used by the FSCI is provided. From this list of indicators, the authors of the FSCI report that high-income countries perform the worst on average of all countries on 'pesticide use' and 'sustainable nitrogen management' (Food Systems Countdown Initiative, 2023). Hence, on a city-regional scale, the change in the percentage of organic food produced and consumed may be a suitable proxy for pesticide use, a key priority in countries participating in FoodCLIC. In addition, significant reductions in land use and nutrient requirements during production can be achieved via a protein transition. Here, an important proxy, related to the RLIs in FoodCLIC, and to the FST, is available in the percentage of plant-based and animal-based protein consumed within each FoodCLIC city-region. An overview of these indicators is provided in table 7.

Table 6: Environmental indicators for global food system sustainability used by the FSCI (2020)

THEMATIC AREA 2: ENVIRONMENT, NATURAL RESOURCES AND PRODUCTION		
CATEGORY	INDICATOR	
Greenhouse gas emissions	Food systems greenhouse gas emissions	Greenhouse gas emissions (kt CO ₂ -equivalents) from food systems
	Greenhouse gas emissions intensity, by product group	Greenhouse gas emissions (kg CO ₂ -equivalents) per kg produced of certain important food commodities (for cereal, rice, beef and cow's milk)
Production	Food product yield, by food group	Yield, or production per unit area (tonnes per ha) or per animal (kg per animal) – an indicator of how efficient production is (for cereal, vegetable, fruit, beef and cow's milk).
Land	Cropland expansion	Average % change in cropland over the previous five years; expanding cropland is a major driver of biodiversity and ecosystem service loss and greenhouse gas emissions.
Water	Agriculture water with-drawal as percent of total renewable water resources	Water withdrawn for irrigation each year, as a percentage of the total renewable water resources available
Biosphere integrity	Functional integrity: Percent agricultural land with minimum level of natural habitat	% of agricultural land area with enough semi-natural or natural habitat, relative to the amount of cropland or rangeland, to maintain biodiversity and functioning ecosystems.
	Fishery health index progress score	An indicator summarizing the availability and sustainability of fish, which are at risk of overfishing or environmental degradation

Pollution	Total pesticides per unit of cropland	The use of pesticides per area of cropland (kg active ingredient per hectare); pesticide use can cause pollution and harm health.
	Sustainable nitrogen management index	A measure of the environmental efficiency of agricultural production.

In addition to the cross-cutting challenges for biodiversity and biogeochemical flows, food systems may be key in local environmental challenges. In the region of Capannori, agricultural land abandonment brings the question of sustainable land management practices to the fore. In the region of Amsterdam, water is certainly a topic in agriculture, but concerns over the quantity of water used for agriculture are perhaps overshadowed by concerns over water quality or soil subsidence in peatlands. Therefore, Living Lab researchers should, in their selection for environmental indicators, combine the need for robust insights into systemic issues, such as biodiversity loss, or changes in biogeochemical flows, with the need for insight into typically local and (policy) relevant environmental challenges. While insights from mapping and gapping may provide a starting point for what these local challenges are, learning questions from policymakers (*how can I make these changes in ..., while I need to maintain the quality of natural areas under the EU habitat directive?*) or citizens give additional insights into the barriers and opportunities for change (and consequently for what needs to be monitored).

Table 7: Overview of suggested proxies for urgent global environmental sustainability applicable to FoodCLIC city-regional food systems.

CATEGORY	SUGGESTED INDICATOR OR PROXY FOR CITY-REGIONS
Pesticide use	% of agricultural land where organic production methods are used (place-based impact)
	% of food consumed that is certified organic
Sustainable nitrogen management	% of plant vs animal protein consumed
	% of land-use in city-region for production of animal protein vs plant protein.

OTHER INDICATORS

In addition to the rigid health indicators and the structured sustainability indicators, additional monitoring will be required to understand the obstacles, facilitators, opportunities, lessons and best practices of each intervention in relation to the city-regional food system. Here, a short guideline is presented on the selection of other indicators. The Living Lab teams decide where, when and how to take the temperature of any given indicator between the baseline, application period and the endline. Purpose, feasibility and the need for an integrated and transdisciplinary approach determine the outline of what can be considered a robust monitoring framework for an intervention.

The Living Lab researchers are advised to draft up monitoring plans for each intervention, based upon the respective action and learning plans. In there, the Living Lab researchers are asked to fill out how they want to monitor health and nutrition, how they want to monitor environmental factors and three other factors.

OBJECTIVES & ACTIONS

The RLIs of FoodCLIC strive to create more healthy and sustainable food environments. To this end, it is important to monitor the effects on health, nutrition and the environment. At the same time, there may be many more objectives of each intervention. Diverse examples of (brief) objectives in the different city-regions are: 'increase collaboration between initiatives', 'improve access to land for (professional) vegetable production for communities', 'support "young" farmers through tools, resources and opportunities'. Monitoring of these objectives is highly contextual. For each RLI, a clear overview of the objectives, the related actions and coupled 'success indicators' can be created. A template for this is available through the 'guidelines for learning and implementation of RLIs'⁴. Based upon this overview, the Living Lab researchers are advised to explicate for whom this indicator shows success and to take into account the diverse ways in which different stakeholders may interpret and action to be successful.

LEARNING QUESTIONS

In addition to the objectives and actions, learning questions collected during co-design and over the course of the interventions are important sources for indicators as well. The development of learning questions is tracked per intervention via the 'DLA Reporting Template Excel'⁴. In addition to the 'bottom-up' learning questions for each RLI, there may be policy-relevant learning questions from local policymakers, that can be connected to particular RLIs. This is considered particularly valuable in light of the experimentation approach in FoodCLIC, as the experiment can directly feed into current policy struggles. In the monitoring plan, Living Lab researchers are asked to indicate which indicators can contribute to develop insight required to answer learning questions coupled to each intervention.

⁴ This template is available internally [here](#). It is made available to the public as part of D1.6 (September 2024) and D1.7 (March 2027).

SYSTEMIC GAPS

Finally, Living Lab researchers have a continuous aim to cultivate the transformative capacity of the RLIs. Several aspects of FoodCLIC set up conditions that facilitate a more transformative atmosphere. The action-learning approach, with the four reflexive learning sessions allows for the continuous improvement of intervention designs. In addition, the CLIC framework fosters an integrated approach towards food systems. However, an important role is present for the Living Lab researcher in providing relevant and transformative insights into the obstacles and barriers, but also in the opportunities for each RLI. The mapping and gapping activities familiarized the Living Lab teams with important systemic gaps in their city-regional food systems. Through visioning, strategizing and co-design, the RLIs should now address some of these gaps. Throughout the development and redesign of these interventions, **Living Lab researchers have to (1) keep track of the RLI's contribution to addressing these systemic gaps and (2) steer RLIs to keep addressing gaps and make use of relevant local opportunities and identified facilitators for transformation.** To this end, the final part of the monitoring template asks Living Lab researchers to list a few indicators per RLI that help keep track of how that RLI addresses systemic gaps, or that help identify systemic opportunities. The templates are available via Appendix B, an example is included in table 8.

Table 8: Dummy version of a monitoring plan for FoodCLIC Amsterdam city-region intervention 1.

RLI NAME	A food circle in Amsterdam Noord (DRAFT)
HEALTH & NUTRITION MONITORING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No <p>If yes, sample size + sampling strategy for this intervention: <i>Estimated 80-100, recruited via food aid and community cooking initiatives that meet up bimonthly for the 'food meet-up Amsterdam North'. All initiatives have between 25 and 140 families that visit weekly. These communities are vulnerable and many people are quite wary of institutions. Therefore, we will work via trusted community leaders and minimize the burden for voluntary participants. Many families are undocumented, therefore we will have to oversample, and accept that some people may not want to leave their contact details.</i></p>
DATA COLLECTION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Basic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Self-perceived general health <input type="radio"/> Experienced food insecurity <input type="radio"/> Dietary quality <input type="radio"/> Extended, specify extra metrics/indicators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> <i>Dietary composition of food aid bags</i> <input type="radio"/> <i>Dietary composition of community kitchen meals</i> <input type="radio"/> <i>Healthy Eating Behaviour Scale</i> <input type="radio"/> _____

ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING

- Yes, via 'Food Sustainability Tool'
 - For 'food waste reduction'
 - For 'dietary shifts'
 - For 'Food mileage reduction' (local food)
- Yes, via context-specific indicators, (specify):
 - Kilograms of food waste prevented/ # meals saved.
 - % of animal-based vs plant-based protein
 - _____
 - _____
- No

Success indicators for (core-) objectives or actions (specify)

Objective/action (selection)	Indicator ('and how may we see that [desired change] is successful?')	Stakeholder who is 'helped' by insights
1. (re)build trust between institutions, food aid initiatives and communities.	1 Perceived mis/distrust with community members. 2 Degree to which 'myths and half-truths' about institutions surface in conversations with community members.	Initiatives, community members Institutions
2. (re)build trust between institutions, food aid initiatives and communities.	1 Perceived mis/distrust with community members. 2 Degree to which 'myths and half-truths' about institutions surface in conversations with community members.	Initiatives, community members Institutions
3. Work towards a physical space for food in Noord (food hub).	3 Establishment of a physical hub where multiple initiatives can organise food waste distribution.	Initiatives, institutions
4. Improve organisational capacity of initiatives.	4 # of initiatives that has built capacity for organisation.	Initiatives, institutions

OTHER INDICATORS

Indicators that help in answering LQs coupled to the RLI (specify)

LQ coupled to RLI (reveal source of LQ)	Indicator
1. How can initiatives improve collaboration with institutions, while funding streams are too inconsistent to maintain a solid organisation? (Initiatives in conversation with municipality)	Increased stability of financial situation initiatives. Increased diversity of funding sources for initiatives.
2. How can food supply to communities be more healthy, while there is not even enough food to serve everyone? (Food aid initiatives)	Size of food supply over time. Composition of food supply over time. Sources of food supplied to the initiative.
3. How can initiatives rely more on local farmer's supply, while they may not even have access to a location around the week? (Local policymakers)	Available farmer's products in region. Willingness of farmer to transport/store food for initiatives.

Indicators that help point out success/outcomes with respect to systemic gaps or that pick up potential opportunities in the CRFS. in the CRFS addressed in this intervention (specify):

Systemic gaps addressed in RLI	Indicator	Potential opportunities identified
1 Food and social security are generally viewed as separate problems with separate fixes.	1 Collaborations between food policy and social policy workers.	-X-
2 Healthiness of food is not considered relevant for food insecure communities.	2 Dietary quality of food aid. 3 Synergy between health and food security.	-X-
-X-	3 # of new urban agriculture initiatives.	Match between fresh food supply and demand of urban agriculture and food aid initiatives.

5. APPLYING THE RMDE FRAMEWORK

5.1 ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS

The iterative and transdisciplinary approach towards the design of RLIs, and the associated monitoring tools have to comply with the ethical standards of the research institutions and FoodCLIC’s Ethical Handbook. The procedures differ significantly across institutions. Based upon the monitoring plans should be able to start ethical procedures in order to get ethical approval before starting the activities.

5.2 REPORTING & TIMELINE

All monitoring activities in FoodCLIC occur as part of work package 3. Therefore, outputs and outcomes of the monitoring process are reported as part of deliverable 3.3 (D3.3), which is due in project month 48 (M48) (September 2026). Monitoring activities, however, are not only relevant towards the end of the intervention period. Instead, monitoring occurs at the start of the interventions, at baseline; it occurs during the interventions, to feed the action-learning spiral; and it occurs after the interventions, the endline. These activities are not subject to external reporting deadlines. This provides the possibility to be flexible and adapt to local dynamics. In some city-regions, ethical approval or baseline recruitment may take longer (unexpectedly). In other city-regions, activities may run into significant speed bumps, such as a changing political environment. Within WP3, there is flexibility to deal with this. However, the project design is also intended to test the FoodCLIC theory of change. This means that the monitoring activities have to be executed in the right order, at approximately the right time and with distance from each other, otherwise the design becomes unworkable. Practically, that means that the Living Lab researchers can use the following timeline for reference.

Figure 5: Timeline of monitoring & related WP3 activities.

5.3 BASELINE

The baseline study is important for two reasons. First, the baseline informs the starting point for each intervention: where are we now and how can we set our targets/goals for the intervention period? The information that is brought forward by the baseline can help to align stakeholders and inform action. In this way, it can feed the first action-reflection cycle. Second, the baseline can be used to assess the effects and outcomes of FoodCLICs involved, through comparison with the endline (see below).

The baseline study is meant to be conducted around the start of the activities of the RLIs (up to and including September 2024) and to encompass: (1) core indicators (see Table 3); (2) health and diet surveys (Appendix 2); (3) context-specific indicators. To understand the full impact of the FoodCLIC Living Lab activities, it is important to conduct the baseline assessment early on. While the core-indicators are not strictly coupled to the activities in the RLIs, it is advised to work out these indicators in the starting phase of the interventions as well. This will help the Living Lab teams to understand how the interventions may contribute to transformative outcomes in for example learning, policy and the SPPI.

While a baseline assessment is set as the minimum for each intervention to allow for comparative analysis, many policy-relevant and socially robust context-specific indicators for RLIs may be monitored continuously. Researchers should aim to maintain a timeframe of approximately 20 months (the duration of the intervention) between baseline and endline. As mentioned, the recruitment of participants for interventions may be slower than expected in some city-regions. It is advised to conduct the baseline measurements as soon as possible in the Living Lab. For some city-regions, it may be possible to start with a subsample and expand from there.

5.4 ENDLINE

The endline assessment includes at least the indicators from the baseline, with the option to include more indicators. This applies both to the core set of indicators that are used to assess the impact and transformative outcomes of the Living Labs, as well as for the context-specific indicators applied in the RLIs. For the core-indicators, the conversation on which indicators to add and leave-out, e.g. which are considered important or effective, is facilitated between the Living Labs during the Monthly-on-the-job support sessions, or via the platform Discourse. For the context-specific indicators, ultimately the decisions on what to include and leave out is decided in collaboration with local policymakers and societal stakeholders.

The endline assessment starts directly after the last action-reflection cycle has taken place in February 2026. Activities for the interventions can continue during the endline assessment. The endline is scheduled to take place between March and May 2026. The Living Lab teams finalize their reports before August 2026.

5.5 CONTINUOUS MONITORING

While the baseline and endline assessments are important, continuous monitoring is required on context-specific indicators for each RLI to feed the action-learning spiral. The reflexive learning sessions provide the space to discuss 'progressing insight' around barriers and obstacles, to strategize based upon the available data and to explore facilitators and opportunities for transformative redesign. In this way, both qualitative and quantitative data that are being collected over the course of the intervention can work as an 'eye-opener' in key moments of redesign.

5.6 DATA MANAGEMENT

Data collection should always follow the outline of the FoodCLIC data management plan. For indicators that are shared across Living Labs, templates are made available to log data. The raw, anonymised data is accessible across the consortium for further analysis. Personalised data is managed at the institution of the Living Lab researcher that has collected the data.

6. LITERATURE

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APPENDIX A: HEALTH & DIET MONITORING

As part of the RMDE framework, the health and diet of participants in real-life interventions (RLIs) will be monitored. It is important to outline how Living Lab researchers (and the team in general) can work with the monitoring tools in their respective city-regions. Therefore, this document outlines which tools should be used, which questions they help to answer and how they can be contextualised and applied locally.

OUTLINE

Each LL-team will at least monitor health, food security and diet quality of **+/-250 participants (approx. 80% food deprived and vulnerable and 50% female)** involved in the RLIs. The purpose of this is to monitor how successful the RLIs manage to improve the healthiness of participants' diets over the course of an intervention. The design of this monitoring is intended to be longitudinal: participants are compared between baseline and endline. There is no comparison against a control group. The figure of 250 was chosen to guarantee a statistically viable sample population, where legitimate changes can be found. It is likely that participants will drop out of the intervention and the monitoring programme. A drop-out rate of approximately 20% has been accounted for in the figure of 250. It is wise to think about containment strategies for high drop-out rates.

It is not important that participants are (equally) distributed across the interventions. Instead, it is important that the health monitoring is applied either where interventions specifically target changes in participants diet, or where effects on their diet and health may be expected. For example, if an intervention is aimed on dietary patterns or intake, it is more valuable to gather information on these health indicators, than if an intervention is aimed at municipality policy makers.

The health and diet quality monitoring rests on three pillars (key questionnaires) that are collated into a standardized FoodCLIC health & diet survey. The three pillars are:

1. General Health
2. Food (in)security
3. Diet quality or dietary diversity

The standardized FoodCLIC health & diet survey is available in a basic outline, in English, for all Living Lab researchers via a link. The overall survey, including the collection of contact details and necessary covariables, should not take more than 15 minutes per participant, this can be done over the phone or in real-life. Separate templates will be created in which raw data can be stored; these will be made available to the Living Lab researchers.

For each pillar in the standardized survey, Living Lab researchers will have to make small adaptations. When parts of the survey are not yet available in the required language, Living Lab

researchers will have to organise the translation. In addition, Living Lab researchers can decide to incorporate additional questions or questionnaires.

Below, you can read the following information per pillar:

- a. What does it aim to monitor and how will it be monitored (e.g. survey)
- b. What is it/what does it comprehend? (e.g. amount of questions, time, source)
- c. What is not captured by this data?
- d. How can it be adapted to the local context?

METADATA

Prior to starting data collection, metadata should be recorded for each research participant. In addition, each research participant should be given a unique ID, accompanied by a 'city-region' code. The metadata should at least record the name of the participant, the contact details, the way in which the survey was administered and the RLI to which data collection is coupled. In addition, basic socio-demographic data needs to be collected, that helps to stratify the sample of participants and allow for comparison beyond the RLI. This includes information about for example age and gender.

GENERAL HEALTH

In FoodCLIC we aim to get an overview of the participants' health at baseline and endline, to see what the current status of the population is and if it changes over time during the intervention period. 'Health' is a broad concept and can be quantified and measured in different ways. To make this measurement low-burden for the participant and researchers and also to avoid collecting unnecessary sensitive data, we chose to measure participants' **self-perceived health status** which you can view as a subjective indication of their current health in general or how (un)healthy they feel at the moment (European Commission. Eurostat., 2013; Galenkamp et al., 2013; Miilunpalo et al., 1997). In FoodCLIC self-perceived health status will be measured on a 5-point Likert scale varying from 'very bad', 'bad', 'fair', 'good', 'very good'. Since this measure is a subjective indication, we decided to add a second health-related question to the core survey which inquires about any existing chronic disease or condition, diagnosed by a medical doctor such as, cardiovascular problems, diabetes, renal dysfunction or cancer(s). Assessing the frequency of chronic diseases in the study population is important for accurately characterizing the sample's health profile. While changes in the prevalence of these conditions over the two-year intervention period are not anticipated, capturing this information enables sensitivity analysis and ensures a comprehensive understanding of the population's health status. The health-related questions are asked immediately after the socio-demographic questions, as additional health related questionnaires can influence the response of a participant to a self-perceived health measurement.

Via these two questions in the survey, FoodCLIC aims to get insight in participants their current perceived health and monitor if this changes over time.

- Self-perceived (“subjective”) Health survey question: “How is your health in general” 5-point Likert scale varying from ‘very bad’ – ‘very good’.
- In the last 12 months, did you suffer from any of the following diseases or conditions diagnosed by a medical doctor? [Myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, high blood pressure, stroke, other cardiovascular diseases, diabetes type 1 or 2, renal disfunction, cancer]?

The questions can be administered via the phone or in person and will only take up a few minutes. Please note that with these survey questions only self-perceived and self-reported health is measured. There will be no collection of medical data. Therefore, the results of these survey questions are prone to bias, common in self-reported measurements.

Living Lab to-do list:

- Think about additional health covariables (e.g., smoking behaviour, BMI, physical activity, stress) to ask about a part of the health pillar.
- Translate the questions from English into the required language and retranslate the result back into English, to check the validity of the translation.

FOOD (IN)SECURITY

Food (in)security will be measured by the **Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)** developed by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (Cafiero et al., 2018; FAO, n.d.). The FIES is a measure of access to food at the level of individuals or households. It measures severity of food insecurity based on people’s responses to questions about constraints on their ability to obtain adequate food. In FoodCLIC, we preferentially use the ‘individual’ level, due to the fact that this aligns with the other survey items of health and dietary quality, which are asked on an individual basis. While food insecurity among children cannot be directly measured using the FIES survey module, it is possible to estimate the percentage of children living in food insecure households. In these cases, Living Lab researchers can decide to deviate from the FoodCLIC preference and use the household level questionnaire. To do so, it is necessary to have data on the number of children in each household surveyed (see Annex II, p. 48, of the [VoH Technical Report No. 1](#) for technical guidance) (FAO, 2016).

The FIES is derived from two widely-used experience-based food security scales: the US Household Food Security Survey Module and the Latin American and Caribbean Food Security Scale (Spanish acronym ELCSA) (Economic Research Service, 2012; Hromi-Fiedler et al., 2009). It consists of a set of eight short yes/no questions asked directly to people regarding the experiences of the last 12 months, typically in face-to-face interviews, although they may be conducted by telephone as well. This scale is adequate to assess the experience of individuals of 15 years or older. The FIES survey module can be administered in a very short time, usually not exceeding 5 minutes, and requires no specialized equipment (such as picture catalogues, scales or rulers). The questions focus on self-reported, food-related behaviors and experiences associated with increasing difficulties in accessing food due to resource constraints.

The FIES is based on a well-grounded construct of the experience of food insecurity composed of three domains:

- Uncertainty/anxiety;
- Changes in food quality; and
- Changes in food quantity.

These domains can be positioned on an underlying scale of severity, as shown for example in Figure A1. The measure of food insecurity associated with a respondent can be located on the scale based on the number of positive responses to the questions (number of behaviours or experiences reported). Such measures are then used to classify respondents into categories of food insecurity severity.

Figure A1. scale of severity of food insecurity according to the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) (FAO,

2024).

The FIES is not intended to quantify food consumption nor does it provide a quantitative assessment of dietary quality. It is not a measure of malnutrition and cannot be used to detect nutritional deficiencies or obesity. Consequently, it is not the appropriate tool for monitoring malnutrition or assessing nutrition-specific outcomes of food security programs and policies.

For the FIES-SM, many valid translations ([link](#) downloads .zip file) are available, which the Living Lab researchers can rely upon. There are [additional resources](#) available, including an [e-learning](#) and more in-depth information about the background of the FIES ([here](#) and [here](#)).

DIET QUALITY

Lastly, to get valid and reliable information about the diet quality at population level, the **Dietary Quality Questionnaire (DQQ)** was selected as one of the core indicators in the RMDE framework. This questionnaire is highly suitable for the context of FoodCLIC. It was originally developed to replace the difficult administration of Food Frequency Questionnaires in low-resource settings, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. The DQQ allows for a rapid assessment of population level dietary quality that can be used to determine 'Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women (MDD-W). This information is currently largely unavailable for European settings, FoodCLIC can contribute to insights about gender specific dynamics and on relatively food deprived and vulnerable groups. At this stage, new indicators have been added, including the non-communicable disease – protect indicator, which is suitable to address the link between diets and health in FoodCLIC RLI.

The DQQ gathers information on consumption over 29 food groups and is designed as a tool for rapid assessments of diet quality of the general population aged 15 years or older (Global Diet Quality Project, 2022, 2024; Herforth et al., 2020; Uyar et al., 2023). Once adapted, the DQQ can be administered via the phone or in person and takes approximately 5 minutes to complete.

In the survey, the different food groups are not mentioned directly but are represented by different sentinel foods. Sentinel foods are the most frequently consumed items within a food group in a given population. These foods capture a large proportion of people who consume any item in that food group. The sentinel food examples for each question are not meant to be an exhaustive list of all possible foods in that food group.

To define the list of sentinel foods for the currently available versions, food items and examples were excluded if it was unnecessary to add them if the respondent would have already said yes to the question based on the other food items. For example, breakfast cereals are typically not mentioned in the 'foods made from grains' category because it would rarely be consumed as the only starchy staple in one day. Also, items that may be confused with other items were excluded. Items that are often consumed in amounts <15g were also excluded from the questionnaire. To summarize, many food items were intentionally excluded because they are not the most common, not necessary after listing the items already in the question, are consumed in amounts <15 grams or are not consistently understood.

Based on the results of the 29 food groups, you can derive the following indicators about diet quality and diet patterns on population level (Global Diet Quality Project, 2022; Herforth et al., 2020, 2023):

- **Minimum Diet Diversity for Women (MDD-W) score:** represents the likelihood of micronutrient adequacy. Validated for women 15-49 years in low- and middle-income countries.
- Consumption of **all five (ALL-5)** recommended food groups.

Table 1. Overview of assessed food groups in Diet Quality Questionnaire (DQQ) (Global Diet Quality Project, 2022)

DQQ Food Groups	
1.	Foods made from grains
2.	Whole grains
3.	White roots, tubers and plantains
4.	Legumes
5.	Vitamin A-rich orange vegetables
6.	Dark green leafy vegetables
7.	Other vegetables
8.	Vitamin A-rich fruits
9.	Citrus
10.	Other fruits
11.	Baked/grain-based sweets
12.	Other sweets
13.	Eggs
14.	Cheese
15.	Yogurt
16.	Processed meats
17.	Unprocessed red meat (ruminant)
18.	Unprocessed red meat (non-ruminant)
19.	Poultry
20.	Fish and seafood
21.	Nuts and seeds
22.	Packaged ultra-processed salty snacks
23.	Instant noodles
24.	Deep fried foods
25.	Fluid milk
26.	Sweet tea/coffee/cocoa
27.	Fruit juice and fruit-flavored drinks
28.	Sugar-sweetened beverages (soft drinks, energy drinks, sport drinks)
29.	Fast food

- **Dietary Diversity scores** for the general population.
- **Global Dietary Recommendations (GDR) score** for the general population
Of which you can compute the **NCD-Protect & NCD-Risk score**.
- It can also give insight into the consumption of specific food groups of interest (on population level), such as: legumes, nuts and seeds, vegetables etc.

	Yesterday, did you eat any of the following foods:	(circle answer)
1	Bread, rice, pasta, tortilla, or cereal?	YES or NO
2	Fresh corn, popcorn, oats, granola, brown rice, or quinoa?	YES or NO
3	Potato?	YES or NO
4	Beans, refried beans, peas, lentils, hummus, chickpeas, tofu, or lima beans?	YES or NO
	Yesterday, did you eat any of the following vegetables:	
5	Carrots, orange squash, pumpkin, sweet potato, or red bell pepper?	YES or NO
6.1	Broccoli, spinach, arugula, kale, collards, turnip greens, or mustard greens?	YES or NO
7.1	Lettuce, tomatoes, green beans, celery, green peppers, cabbage, or cucumber?	YES or NO
7.2	Zucchini, mushrooms, eggplant, cauliflower, okra, asparagus, or radish?	YES or NO

Figure 2. Example of Diet Quality Questionnaire (DQQ) United States version including food groups 1-7 sentinel foods in questionnaire (Global Diet Quality Project, 2023)

The DQQ is validated on population level and does *not* measure individual dietary intake. Furthermore, the DQQ does not capture all aspects of the diet, only the 29 selected food groups.

The DQQ is not yet contextualized for all the FoodCLIC regions, but a large variety of DQQs is available. To adapt the DQQ to local level, requires for the questionnaire to be translated to the required language, but also for sentinel foods to be adapted, to reflect the dietary patterns of the target population. To make these adaptations, there are two possible approaches. In some countries, food consumption statistics are available. These statistics can be used to select appropriate sentinel foods. For a validated questionnaire, these sentinel foods would have to be tested thoroughly. A different possible method, is to use expert community leaders, to develop DQQs that are more specific to a particular target population, that may eat a diet which differs from the national average. However, it is not possible to simply add foods, as the questionnaire would no longer reflect the most commonly eaten foods in that food groups. To make these adaptations, nutrition knowledge is required, to avoid foods from being added to an incorrect food group. Therefore, a check back or local collaboration with nutrition experts is highly recommended, to ensure the validity of the questionnaire. More information about the adaptation and use of the DQQ can be found online. Here you find [general info](#), [tools](#), [tutorial slides](#) and [guides for indicator calculation](#). General info can be found [here](#). Tools required for administering the DQQ [here](#). Tutorial slides [here](#) and written methods for the calculation of indicators here.

Researcher to-do for DQQ

1. Translate questionnaire to the required language.
2. Consult with a regional/national nutrition experts to see if sentinel foods are representative for your country or that you need to adapt it. Take into account the nutrient compositions measured by the food group and sentinel foods.

3. If the DQQ is adapted and contextualized for your research population, you need to re-translate it to English and share it with RMDE involved nutrition scientists, from VU, or ULisboa-FM to confirm the (nutritional) validity.

Literature appendix A

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APPENDIX B

GUIDE TO MONITORING PLAN CONTENTS

This monitoring template helps you as a researcher in developing a monitoring plan for a specific intervention. The first table contains guiding questions/considerations for drafting the monitoring plan. The second table can be filled out based upon the description in the first and enables you to create an overview of which aspects you are monitoring for each intervention. This is not the only resource that is available. There are resources coupled to the guidelines for implementing and learning from interventions that include an RLI action plan template, a DLA Learning Question log sheet and a DLA reporting template per intervention (and a separate tab for the CoP policymakers).

Table B1: Guide to monitoring plan

Suggestion and guidance for monitoring plan per RLI (start of intervention)		
Section 1: Health & nutrition		
Will there be monitoring of health and nutrition data for this RLI?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No, this intervention does not address any/enough/significant objectives, LQs or systemic gaps around health and nutrition. 2. Yes, because this type of information is directly requested by societal stakeholders and/or its part of core-objectives in the RLI 3. Yes, because there are (policy-relevant) LQs connected to this RLI that would require this type of monitoring. 4. Yes, because this intervention originates from a systemic gap in the city-region food system on this topic. 	<p>To-do</p> <p>Option 1: Ensure coverage of health & nutrition is arranged somewhere else, continue to next section.</p> <p>Option 2 – 4: Determine what kind of health & nutrition information is required.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Basic (food security, dietary quality, self-perceived health) ○ Basic + additional information <p>Determine the possible sample size.</p> <p>Determine a sampling strategy</p>
Section 2: Environmental indicators		
Will there be monitoring of environmental indicators for this RLI?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No, this intervention does not address any/enough/significant environmental topics through its objectives, LQs or systemic gaps. 2. Yes, because this type of information is directly requested by societal stakeholders and/or its part of core-objectives in the RLI. 	<p>To-do</p> <p>Option 1: Consider whether the intervention addresses co-benefits. How is environmental sustainability coupled to the intervention, will this come up during re-design? – next section</p> <p>Option 2-4:</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Yes, because there are (policy-relevant) LQs on this topic that can be connected to this RLI. 4. Yes, because this intervention originates from a systemic gap in the city-region food system on this topic. 	Continue to next question.
What type of environmental monitoring should be conducted?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GHG emissions of changes in the food environment and the food system. Specifically on the topics of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Food waste reduction b. Dietary shifts c. Food mileage reduction. 2. Other global environmental challenges of food systems (e.g. biodiversity loss, land-use change, water use). 3. Specific local environmental challenges (these may include all challenges that occur globally, but require more specific monitoring) 	<p>To-do</p> <p>Option 1: Design monitoring and data-collection plan together with CMCC and other Living Lab teams involved in similar RLIs</p> <p>Option 2: Consider the use of standardised indicators from other indicator frameworks such as: CRFS sustainability indicator framework, Food System Dashboard.</p> <p>Option 3: Self-design of indicators, based upon LQs, objectives/actions or systemic gaps. Example: <i>Change in % of urban agriculture projects applying organic methods of food production.</i></p>
Section 3: Other indicators		
Which indicators are coupled to the (core-) objectives and/or actions of the RLI?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Success indicators for societal stakeholders, coupled to (core-) objectives and/or actions of the RLIs. 2. Success indicators for policymakers, coupled to (core-) objectives and/or actions of the RLIs. 3. Success indicators for researchers, coupled to (core-) objectives and/or actions of the RLIs. 	To-do Refer to the RLI action plan, list actions and objectives and their related indicators and specify for whom this is a success indicator. Based upon that overview, reflect on who is helped by the monitoring and adjust/add indicators to reflect stakeholders.
Which indicators are useful to answer LQs?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Indicators that help in finding answers to LQs articulated by local policymakers coupled to the RLI (connections to be made by researcher). 2. Indicators that help in finding answers to LQs articulated by societal stakeholders coupled to the RLI. 	List LQs for each intervention, see also DLA reporting template and link specific indicator that would enable these learning questions to be (partly) resolved. Be mindful of the fact that LQs are not first-order questions about information/data, instead they refer to systemic barriers.
Which indicators are suitable to see how the RLI addresses systemic gaps?	Indicators that point towards how RLIs take up systemic gaps, or pick up potential opportunities in the CRFS.	List systemic gaps addressed through RLI and add potential indicators for success. Also mentioned indicators that could harvest new opportunities for RLIs

MONITORING PLAN – EMPTY TEMPLATE

Table B2: Empty template to fill out monitoring plans per RLI

RLI Name	_____																					
Health & nutrition monitoring	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No If yes, sample size + sampling strategy for this intervention: _____																					
Data collection	<input type="radio"/> Basic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Self-perceived general health <input type="radio"/> Experienced food insecurity <input type="radio"/> Dietary quality <input type="radio"/> Extended, specify extra metrics/indicators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> _____ <input type="radio"/> _____ <input type="radio"/> _____ <input type="radio"/> _____ 																					
Environmental monitoring	<input type="radio"/> Yes, via Food Sustainability Tool <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> For 'food waste reduction' <input type="radio"/> For 'dietary shifts' <input type="radio"/> For 'Food mileage reduction' (local food) <input type="radio"/> Yes, via context-specific indicators, (specify): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> _____ <input type="radio"/> _____ <input type="radio"/> _____ <input type="radio"/> _____ <input type="radio"/> No																					
Other indicators	Success indicators for (core-) objectives or actions (specify) <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 10px;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 33%;">Objective/action</th> <th style="width: 33%;">Indicator ('and how may we see that [desired change] is successful?')</th> <th style="width: 33%;">Stakeholder</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1.....</td> <td>1.....</td> <td>.....</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.....</td> <td>2.....</td> <td>.....</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.....</td> <td>3.....</td> <td>.....</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Indicators that help in answering LQs coupled to the RLI (specify)</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 10px;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 40%;">LQ coupled to RLI (reveal source of LQ)</th> <th style="width: 60%;">Indicator</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1.....</td> <td>1.....</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.....</td> <td>2.....</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.....</td> <td>3.....</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Objective/action	Indicator ('and how may we see that [desired change] is successful?')	Stakeholder	1.....	1.....	2.....	2.....	3.....	3.....	LQ coupled to RLI (reveal source of LQ)	Indicator	1.....	1.....	2.....	2.....	3.....	3.....
Objective/action	Indicator ('and how may we see that [desired change] is successful?')	Stakeholder																				
1.....	1.....																				
2.....	2.....																				
3.....	3.....																				
LQ coupled to RLI (reveal source of LQ)	Indicator																					
1.....	1.....																					
2.....	2.....																					
3.....	3.....																					

Indicators that help point out success/outcomes with respect to systemic gaps in the CRFS addressed in this intervention (specify):

Systemic gaps addressed in RLI	Indicator	Potential opportunities identified
1.....	1.....	-X-
2.....	2.....	-X-
-X-	3.....

PARTNERS

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